

Rapid Risk Assessment - Analysis of Active Directory Services

Andrea Covello

Defense Department, scip AG
anco@scip.ch
<https://www.scip.ch>

Marc Ruef (Editor)

Research Department, scip AG
maru@scip.ch
<https://www.scip.ch>

Keywords: Active Directory, AD, Assessment, Backup, Cybersecurity, Detect, DRM, Exchange, Firewall, Framework

1. Preface

This paper was written in 2017 as part of a research project at scip AG, Switzerland. It was initially published online at <https://www.scip.ch/en/?labs.20170216> and is available in English and German. Providing our clients with innovative research for the information technology of the future is an essential part of our company culture.

2. Introduction

In my work as security consultant I'm involved in *security architecture reviews* and *assessments*. They are sometimes limited on single application other times it may involve the whole DMZ implementation or a complex framework. The goal is to evaluate the risks and propose strategies to mitigate them. But as in real life, seldom the analyzed assets are isolated from the environment. That's why we need to *define scopes* to limit effort and costs, but sometimes it just doesn't feel right. Imagine a security review/assessment of an application/service that is integrated within the *Active Directory Services* (ADS): How can I provide conclusive results without assessing the ADS architecture & concepts?

3. Role of Active Directory

Unless you're not on a complete non-Windows environment, you have to deal with ADS – In my 20+ years of Cybersecurity services I've seen very few environments that didn't. ADS is almost omnipresent and plays a central role not only in authentication. My first question on such assessment usually is: "What happens when the ADS is down?" Most people answer that the ADS is redundant and high-available and in turn I say: "Well, I didn't speak of server disruption, I meant – what if the AD is malfunctioning, corrupted or just not available – How will your business process be affected?" Usually at this stage most people realize the impact. The network may be up and running, the storage services available and even the virtual or physical infrastructure (VDI, servers, workstations) working and still you may not be able to access your workstation, check for your email.

4. Rapid Risk Assessment

The ADS is a critical target, by now you'll agree that that the Cybersecurity posture of the ADS will affect any application or solution that relies on it, therefore we always suggest to also reviewing the ADS implementation for cybersecurity risks. Still, there is an issue: Normally an ADS assessment would require at least 5 days effort. You see the problem on hitting the budget.

Therefore we came with a different approach: Adapting the *NIST Cybersecurity Framework* [1] for our Risk Assessment. The CSF approach is explained in this picture:

Figure: NIST CSF Lifecycle

Security is a process: It starts with the *identification* of our critical assets and its related governance, going further to implementing controls to *protect* and *detect* cybersecurity events, and (to complete the cycle) you'll need to have procedures and processes to *respond* during and *recover* after cybersecurity events. Our *Rapid Risk Assessment* [2] is following this schema to establish information about the security controls available in each area and its *maturity* [3] level.

To achieve the time-frame restriction the assessment is mainly based on interviews with ADS key stake holders and on automated information gathering (using scripted

tools). Those steps should have given enough information to be analyzed and documented in 2 days.

4.1. ADS Security Categories

Following categories will be of interest when assessing the Active Directory Security Controls:

Category	Subcategories	CSF Area
Risk Assessment	Business Impact Analysis, Data Classification, Infrastructure Impact Analysis	IDENTIFY
Architecture Design	Topology, Forest, Domain, Site, DC, FSMO, DNS, Clients	IDENTIFY
Extended Services	Certificate, Federation, Rights Management (DRM)	IDENTIFY
Integration	Exchange, Skype (UC), Sharepoint, Hyper-V	IDENTIFY
Authentication	Local, Remote, Privileged	PROTECT
Administration	Local, Remote, Service Providers	PROTECT
Group Policies	Design, Testing, Operation	PROTECT
System Hardening	Baseline, Firewall, Integrity Check	PROTECT
Client Access	Local, Remote, Service Providers	PROTECT
Protocol Encryption	LDAP, Global Catalog, Kerberos, SMB	PROTECT
Life-Cycle	Patching, Change-Management, Backup	PROTECT
Logging & Audit	Policies, Collection, Archiving, Normalization	DETECTION
Monitoring	Network Monitoring, Intrusion Detection, Security Monitoring, Vulnerability Management	DETECTION
Incident Response Management	ADS Process & Procedures	RESPONSE

ADS Recovery	Object Restore, Function Restore, CA Certificate Restore, ADS Disaster Recovery	RECOVER
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The ADS assessment will analyze each category and report a risk level based on the information gathered during the process. Key effort of this approach is to understand the avenues for establishing a healthy ADS, implementing monitoring systems, reducing the attack surface and managing a resilient environment.

4.2. Execution and Deliverables

To give a rough figure of the required efforts, this table will give you a quick overview:

Effort	What	Note
3h	Interview with key stakeholders	Planned initial 2h interview – 1h as contingency and further clarification
1h	Request for ADS configuration & documentation	Export GPO from DC & clients – Get available documentation
4h	Automated AD information gathering	Requires a windows workstation with read privileges to the AD and a running PowerShell environment, to run our scripts
4h	Data Analysis	Where the magic happens... :)
4h	Reporting	Fill the issues on a predefined Template

Now an overview on the deliverables, this is how the report may look like in the overall survey matrix:

5 Survey

Note: explanation on STATUS rating is described in chapter 9.7

5.1 Active Directory Assessment Results

ID	Description	Status	CSF Area
ID	Inventory, Governance & Architecture		Identify
	1. Risk Assessment	MEDIUM	
	2. Architecture Design	LOW	
	3. Certificate Services (PKI)	MEDIUM	
	4. Right Management Services (DRM)	PASSED	
	5. Exchange Integration	PASSED	
	6. Unified Communication (Skype) Integration	LOW	
	7. Sharepoint Integration	MEDIUM	
	8. Hyper-V Integration	MEDIUM	
	9. Federation Integration	N/A	
10. Cloud Integration (Azure, AWS, GCL)	N/A		
PR	Protection		Protect
	1. Authentication	PASSED	
	2. Administration	HIGH	
	3. User Permissions	LOW	
	4. Services & System Drivers	LOW	
	5. Group Policies (GPO)	MEDIUM	
6. Registry Key Settings	PASSED		

Figure: Rapid Security Assessment ADS Overview

And this is how a finding may look like:

ID	Finding	Description
DE-3	DETECTION	
	3. Host intrusion detection system (HIDS) not in use	No intrusion detection technology is implemented on DC host system level
	References:	Intrusion detection methods should be supported by specialist software, such as host Intrusion Detection Systems and Network Intrusion Detection systems. [CF.10.06.05, <i>The Standard of Good Practice for Information Security</i>] Employ automated tools to continuously monitor workstations, servers, and mobile devices with anti-virus, anti-malware, personal firewall, and host-based IDS functionality. All intrusion detection agents should be

Figure: Rapid Security Assessment ADS Finding

5. Conclusion

The *Rapid Risk Assessment* approach will not find all possible issues inside your ADS, but will surely point you in the right direction and highlight major gap that may harm your environment. Probably the final results would recommend investing more time in a specific category inspection, but at least you'll spend precious time and resources in the most effective way.

6. External Links

- [1] <https://www.nist.gov/cyberframework>
- [2] <https://www.scip.ch/en/?labs.20161124>
- [3] https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Capability_Maturity_Model